

THOT THEORY OF TONE

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On the basis of the Version 7c of the Questionnaire

Mwan. Analytical report on the tonal system

1. General information about the language

Information on the tonology and grammar of Mwan can be found in the following publications: (Bolli & Flik 1978; Perekhvalskaya 2004; Perekhvalskaya 2007; Perekhvalskaya 2010; Perekhvalskaya 2011; Perekhvalskaya 2014; Perekhvalskaya & Yegbé 2018). However, the analysis of the tonal system presented here is different from those found in the preceding publications.

1.1. Language name

The autolinguonym is Mwan /bũã/. ISO 639-3 moa. Glottolog code: mwan1250. Mona, the name used by the neighbouring Jula, also appears in official documents. The neighbouring Wan refer to Mwan as *gããgòdê*.

1.2. Genetic affiliation

Mwan belongs to the South Mande group (< Southeastern Mande < Mande < Niger-Congo). It is spoken mainly in the central part of the Republic of Côte d'Ivoire (West Africa) in about 20 villages. The number of the L1 speakers is more than 20,000. Most of the Mwan speak Jula as their second language, those living in urban centers speak French.

1.3. Dialects

Mwan varieties spoken in different villages are characterized by certain peculiarities in lexicon and in pronunciation, however, in general, dialectal variation within Mwan is low.

2. Segmental phonology

2.1. Phonemic inventory

2.1.1. Vowels

oral				nasal		
		front	back			
high		i	u	high	ĩ	ũ
mid	upper-mid	e	o	mid	ẽ	õ
	lower-mid	ɛ	ɔ		low	ã
low		a				

Table 1. Vowels

The phoneme /ŋ/ is considered a vowel on the following grounds: 1) it alone can constitute a foot of the V type (*ŋ* 'I, me'); 2) it may occur in the foot Auslaut; 3) it carries a tone (*dĩŋ* 'neighbour', *yèŋ* 'you > me'). *ŋ* is a vowel of restricted distribution, it cannot be immediately preceded by a consonant (i.e., feet of the C_ŋ or CL_ŋ types are disallowed).

Phonetically, all vowels except for /ŋ/ can be short or long. Most often, both vowels of a CVV or VV feet are identical, although the sequences iV, eV, εV, uV, oV, ɔV are also possible. Vowels /i/, /e/, /ε/ and /u/, /o/, /ɔ/, when followed by a different vowel in a foot CVV, are realized in the normal register as [ĩ] and [ũ] respectively. These vowels are realized fully in a slow pronunciation or in the chanting mode. Cf. in Perfective: *kú* ‘to catch’ – *kúã* ‘(he) caught’; *dē* ‘to kill’ – *dã* ‘(he) killed’.

Long vowels are interpreted as combinations of two identical vowels on the following grounds:

1) A morphemic boundary can be traced inside a long vowel. This occurs in the perfective form with verbs of the Ca or Cã structure when the final vowel of the verb is followed by the perfective suffix -à/-ã: *kpá* ‘to put’, Prf. *à kpàà* ‘(he) put it’; *yã* ‘to finish’ – *yãã* ‘(he) finished’.

2) In normal tempo speech, long vowel *aa* can be formed at the junction of words if a full-valued word (usually, a verb) is followed by a non-subject pronoun *à*:

- (1) *gbē kpá à kóó* [gbē kpàà kóó]
 hand put 3Sg at
 ‘to shake hand with somebody’.

2.1.2. Consonants

		Labial	Apical	Palatal	Velar	Labiovelar
Stops	Unvoiced	p	t		k	kp
	Voiced	b	d		g	gb
Affricates	Unvoiced			tʃ		
	Voiced			dʒ		
Fricatives	Unvoiced	f	s			
	Voiced	v	z			
Implosives and Glides		ɓ [ɓ, m]	ɗ [ɗ, l, r, n]	j [j, ɲ]		w [w, ẽ]

Table 2. Consonants

Any consonant can occupy the foot-initial position. Only /ɗ/ is allowed in the foot-internal position in the CLVV, CLVŋ types of foot.

The nasal or oral realizations of the phonemes /ɗ/, /ɓ/, /j/¹ and /w/ depend on the nasal / oral quality of the vowel they precede.

Mwan consonants do not exert a tone depressor effect.

2.2. Prosodic units

2.2.1. Syllable

The tone bearing unit is a syllable. Syllables may have the following structures: V, CV, CLV.

2.2.2. Foot

The main prosodic unit in Mwan is prosodic foot which may consist of one or two syllables. The allowed foot structures are: V, VV, CV, CVV (including CVŋ), CLVV (including CLVŋ). The type CLVV can be optionally realized CvLV (in other words, a reduced copy of the vowel can be inserted between the initial vowel and L), and the vowel length is optional on the surface: *kdũu* [klù] ~ [klù:] ~ [k^ulù] ‘owl’). However, its vowel is phonologically double, which fact is confirmed, in particular, by the mode of Imperative-Optative formation (see §7.1.2): *bdãã* ‘to swell’ → *bdãã* ‘swell!’ (if it were a single vowel, one would expect **bdã* as the imperative form).

The distribution of the foot types by word classes is shown in Table 3.

Foot structure	Word classes
V	only in personal pronouns, functional words, interjections
VV	a couple of particles; no content words
CV	all word classes
CVV	all word classes
CLVV	content word classes

¹ In accordance with established tradition, further on, the phoneme /j/ is denoted by the letter “y”.

Table 3. Foot types

The subtypes CV η and CLV η of the types CVV and CLVV are not found among verbs.

The **nasalization** is a characteristic of the entire foot. In a nasal foot, all its elements (consonants and vowels) are nasalized, and in an oral foot, all the elements are non-nasalized. The foot-final vowel η is neutral with respect to the feature of orality/nasality; it can appear in both oral and nasal feet.

There are constraints concerning combinations of semi-open (/ɛ/, /ɔ/) and semi-closed (/e/, /o/) vowels in the CVV foot: a V₁ /ɛ/ cannot co-occur with a V₂ /e/ and /o/, while a V₁ /e/ does not co-occur with a V₂ /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ (in other words, both vowels in a heavy foot should be either semi-closed or semi-open).

Most often, morpheme limits coincide with the foot boundaries, but there are cases when a foot contains two morphemes. In particular, in perfective, a verbal form of the CVV structure (representing one foot) may consist of the perfective suffix *-a/-ã* and a CV root:

dǎ́ ‘give’ → *dǎ́-ǎ́* ‘give-PFV’,

kǔ́ ‘catch’ → *kǔ́-ǎ́* ‘catch-PFV’.

2.2.3. Word

A word may consist of one foot or several feet. Words containing more than one foot are represented mainly by compounds (e.g. *dǎ́á|gdǎ́ǎ́* ‘elder brother’ < *dǎ́á* ‘elder brother’ + *gdǎ́ǎ́* ‘male’); words with suffixes (e.g. *yē-wó-bí* ‘worker’ < *yē* ‘work’, *wó* ‘do’, *bí* agentive suffix) or, more rarely, prefixes (in particular, pref. *é-* of predicative adjectives); reduplicated words, loanwords (e.g. *sǎ́áká* < Manding *sáráká* ‘sacrifice’ < Arabic *ṣadaqa*). There is also a certain number of presumably native words consisting of two or more feet which do not exist in Mwan as separate words, e.g.: *gdǎ́|wò* ‘hyena’.

Of special interest are so-called “*dǎ́*-verbs”. They result from an ancient derivation, e.g. *dūdǎ́* ‘to stop’, where *-dǎ́* is a derivative suffix of a vague semantics, and the stem *dū* does not appear as a separate word. These verbs display certain particularities in their tonal behavior. There are 15 verbs in of this type (out of the total number of 415 verbs in the Mwan dictionary (Perekhval'skaya & Yegbé 2018)), mainly with a toneless stem (*budǎ́* ‘bend down’, *kudǎ́* ‘bend down’, *dǎ́ǎ́* ‘turn around’, *piidǎ́* ‘be scattered’, *pidǎ́* ‘jump’, *tidǎ́* ‘blacken’, *yadǎ́* ‘sit down’, *yidǎ́* ‘lie down’), sometimes with M-toned stem (*bādǎ́* ‘fell’, *bīdǎ́* ‘lift, raise’, *gbīdǎ́* ‘roar’, *dūdǎ́* ‘stop’, *jīdǎ́* ‘go away’, *zīdǎ́* ‘come down’), and one instance of a H-toned stem (*kpádǎ́* ‘stretch out’; the tone of the suffix is H, in agreement with the H Toneme Copy Rule, see §6.1.1).

To this group can be added the compound verb *dǎ́ciè* ‘cook’ (< *dǎ́* ‘put’, *ciè* ‘on the fire’) and two verbs presumably resulting from fusion of the verbal stems with the derivative suffix *dǎ́* (this suffix appears in some forms of their paradigm): *kdǎ́á* ‘overturn, capsize’ and *kǎ́á* ‘walk’. Their tonal behavior follows the same model as that of the *dǎ́*-verbs.

There are also some compound verbs consisting of an originally nominal stem² followed by an originally verbal stem, e.g. *sǎ́sí* ‘to laugh’ (< *sǎ́* ‘tooth’, *sí* ‘take’). In such verbs (“N+V compound verbs”), verbal inflection concerns only the verbal stems (see §7).

3. Tones and tonemes inventory

3.1. Character of tones

Mwan has a level-tone system.

3.1.1. Number of levels

Mwan has three level tones, H, M and L. Examples of minimal triples: *kùè* ‘badger’, *kūē* ‘wing bean’ (a tree), *kúé* ‘load’; *kàà* ‘file (tool)’, *kāā* ‘fish’, *káá* ‘to scratch’.

3.1.2. Contours hosted by one TBU

The falling contour can be hosted by a single syllable as a result of the spread of the high tone of the final syllable of the preceding word. The spread of the high tone on a short vowel happens in only one case,

² In some cases, the first component is not attested as a separate word in Mwan.

when the postposition/preverb *dā* ‘under, in’ is preceded by a H-toned element, as in (2a). In (2b), the same postposition is in a context where it is not preceded by the H tone.³

- (2a) *kpáá é dā*
 shed ART under
 ‘under the shed’
 (2b) *dīī dō dā*
 tree one under
 ‘under a tree’

3.2. Inventory of tonemes

3.2.1. Level tonemes

There are three tonemes in Mwan: High (v̂), Mid (v̄) and Low (v̇). Their tonemic statuses are based on the following criteria.

H toneme

The Tonal Morpheme Criterion. H tone can be regarded as a grammatical tonal morpheme of the Contrastive pronominal series, cf. Non-subject series 3Sg *à* – Contrastive non-subject 3Sg. *á*.

The Shared TBU Criterion. H can share one TBU with L in the postposition *dā*, see (2a).

The Activity Criterion. H toneme can be copied, as in (3b); in more detail, see §6.1.1, 6.1.2.

- (3a) *dē dōō*
 woman husband
 ‘a woman’s husband’

- (3b) *é dōō*
 2SG husband
 ‘your husband’

H toneme can be spread, see §6.1.5.

M toneme

The Floating Criterion. A floating M tone is prefixed to the L-toned “constant” lexemes, it is suffixed to the 3sg. pronouns; it also appears as an Imperative-Optative suffix, see §7.1.2.

The Tonal Morpheme Criterion. M toneme is the marker:

– of the Habitual Aspect: *kú* ‘to catch’ – *kū* ‘(he) catches’; *wè* ‘to speak’ – *wē* ‘(he) speaks’; *bdāā* ‘to swell’ – *bdāā* ‘(it) swells. For details, see §7.1.1;

– of the Imperative-Optative for CVV-verbs, see §7.1.2.

L toneme

The Tonal Morpheme Criterion. L is the tonal component of the Affirmative Perfective morpheme which can be represented as ^L-*dā*/^L-*dā*/^L-*à*/^L-*ā*. This L grammatical tone is mapped onto the entire verbal stem plus the perfective suffix (if it follows the verbal stem immediately): *kú* ‘to catch’ – *kūā* ‘caught’; *gāā* ‘to hide’ – *gāāā* ‘hid, hidden’; *bùè* ‘to miss (an aim)’ – *bùèdā* ‘missed’.

The Shared TBU Criterion: L can share one TBU with H in the postposition *dā*, see (2a).

The Activity Criterion: Within a tonal phrase, the L toneme is copied on the subsequent toneless segment, see §6.1.3; it causes a contrastive effect and raises the tone of the first syllable of the subsequent word belonging to the mobile type, see §6.1.4 and §8.2.

3.2.2. The question of contour tonemes

As mentioned in §3.1.2, a falling contour can be hosted by one syllable. However, this contour does not meet any criterion for contour tonemes: it is composed of the levels available in Mwan as tonemes (contrary to the the Non-Compositionality Criterion); it results from the process of the spread of the High tone (contrary to the Single TBU criterion).

Therefore, the falling contour in Mwan is not a toneme, it is a combination of two level tonemes.

³ In previous publications, perfective affirmative forms of two irregular verbs, *ye* ‘see’ and *kdé* ‘do’, were also mentioned as the instances of realization of a HL contour on a single syllable, *yā* and *kdā* respectively. However, the correct phonological interpretation of these affirmative perfective forms preceded by a H are *yāā* and *kdāā* (and, by the way, the basic form of the verb ‘do’ is also disyllabic, *kdēē*, see §2.2.2).

3.3. Floating tones

There is a M floating tone in Mwan (further on, it is marked as an indexed hash, e.g.: #*bòò* ‘forest’). It is prefixed to the L-toned “constant” lexemes, it is suffixed to the 3sg. pronouns; it also appears as an Imperative-Optative suffix, see §7.1.2. It manifests itself as follows:

- the floating M prohibits tonal spread or toneme copying. I.e., if a potential controller word has a suffixed floating M (subject 3sg. pronoun *è[#]*, non-subject 3sg. pronoun *à[#]*, 3pl. pronouns *ò[#]*), its tone is not copied to the right. If a word has a prefixed floating M (e.g., it belongs to the “constant” type), it cannot be target for the rightward tonal spread or toneme copying;
- if the verbal stem is represented by a heavy foot (CVV or CLVV), the floating M suffix of Imperative-Optative is docked on its final vowel, see §7.1.2.

3.4. Downdrift and downstep

There is no meaningful downstep or downdrift.

3.5. Upstep

There is no upstep.

3.6. Other suprasegmental features of tonemes, apart from pitch

There are no suprasegmental features in Mwan apart from pitch.

4. Tonotactics: tonal span, tonal phrase

4.1. Tonal span limits

4.1.1. Tonal span size

The minimal size of tonal span is ½ of a syllable (in the rare cases where HL contour appears on monosyllabic foot as a result of H tone spread, see §3.1.2, §3.2.2). The maximal size of tonal span equals 4 syllables, this happens in only one unfrequent context: when H tone spreads on the affirmative perfective form of a mobile *dá*-verb whose verbal stem is represented by a heavy foot, see §2.2.3, §6.1.5, §7.1.3.3. Most currently, tonal span equals one or two syllables.

If both syllables of a heavy foot bear identical tones, we consider these tones as realization of one toneme, e.g. /l̄ɛɛ/ [M l̄ɛɛ] ‘year’.⁴ If tones of the syllables constituting a foot are different, they represent two different tonemes, and the foot includes two spans, e.g. /d̄ɔ̄ɔ̄/ [L d̄ɔ̄][H ɔ̄] ‘trunk’ (of elephant).

Underlyingly, a heavy foot can host two identical tonemes, in this case the H Toneme Copy Rule, the L Toneme Copy Rule and the L Toneme Dissimilation Rule target only the first toneme, e.g.: *kpàà* [L kpà][L à] ‘dry’ → *bádòò kpàà* ‘dry rice’. Otherwise, a heavy foot can host one toneme, in which case the rules concern both syllables of the foot, e.g. *kòò* [L kòò] ‘hand’ → *d̄ɛ kóó* ‘child’s hand’. On this topic, see also §8.2.

4.1.2. Change of limits of a tonal span

When the H Tone Spread Rule is applied, a H toneme extends across the boundary of a foot, see §6.1.5.

4.1.3. Tonal spans and other units

Tonal span prototypically coincides with a syllable or a foot (and it is difficult to decide which one of these units is more prototypical). There are numerous feet to which two different tonemes are associated, see §4.2.

If however both syllables of a heavy foot carry identical tones on surface, they are considered as belonging to one tonal span. This is true even for those heavy feet whose syllables are ascribed separate tonemes at the underlying level, so that tonal modifications concern only their initial syllables, like in the word *d̄ɔ̄ɔ̄* ‘husband’ [L d̄ɔ̄ɔ̄], cf. (4) where syllables of this foot belong to different tonal spans because of the H tone copy rule.

$$(4) \quad \begin{array}{l} \acute{y} \quad \acute{d}\acute{o}\acute{o} \\ \text{1SG} \quad \text{husband} \end{array} = [\text{H } \acute{y}][\text{H } \acute{d}\acute{o}][\text{L } \acute{o}]$$

⁴ Alternatively, two identical tonemes can be ascribed to each syllable of a heavy foot at the underlying level, with a subsequent merger of these tonemes according to the toneme fusion rule, see §6.1.6 and §8.2. In any case, and on the surface, two identical tones on a heavy foot always belong to one tonal span.

‘my husband’

A tonal span can exceed the limits of a foot as a result of application of the H Tone Spread Rule, see §6.1.5. Besides, a L toneme (being the tonal exponent of the Perfective Affirmative marker) extends over the verbal stem and the Perfective suffix. If the verbal stem is represented by a heavy foot, the suffix appears as a separate foot *dā*; in this case, the tonal span of the L toneme includes two feet (the verbal stem + the suffix), see §7.1.3.

4.2. Combinations of tonemes

A heavy foot may contain one or two tonal spans, see §4.1. When such a foot hosts two different tonemes, all six imaginable melodies (i.e. combinations of different tonemes) are available:

HL: *fōŋ* ‘fault’,

LH: *kòó* ‘we, us’,

MH: *tāá* ‘you should’

ML: *tāà* ‘or (particle)’

HM: *kpáā* ‘tree (sp.)’

LM: *blòō* ‘cane rat’.

There are also heavy feet where the first syllable is toneless, and the second one carries a L toneme, e.g.: *dòò* ‘place’.

The frequency of the melodies varies considerably, the most frequent being HL and LH (i.e. the most contrastive combinations). The least frequent is the melody ML ($\bar{v}\grave{v}$) attested only for CVV feet and not available for the CLVV type.

In CVV and CLVV verbs, when speaking of lexical tones, only identical tones are licensed on both syllables (i.e., a verbal stem can carry only one toneme, if no tonal processes are involved). In heavy feet adjectives, combinations of heterogeneous tonemes are rare.

Words consisting of two (or more) feet bear no specific melodies. The only exception is represented by “*dā*-verbs” (see §2.2.3). All such verbs consist of two feet, the initial one most often with lexical M tone or toneless, and the derivative suffix *-dā* is low-toned. These verbs have their specific inflectional model, see §7.1.3.2.

4.3. Toneless syllables and morphemes

4.3.1. Toneless syllables

Lexically toneless syllables and feet can obtain their tonemes through the H and L Toneme Copy Rules (see §6.1.2, 6.1.3); they can be tonalized by replacive tonal morphemes, see §7.1.1 and §7.1.3. Otherwise, they acquire a default M tone which is not considered a toneme.

There is one toneless grammatical morpheme, the affirmative perfective suffix *-a/-dā*. For the rules of its tonalization, see §7.1.3.

4.3.2. Toneless morphemes

The only toneless morpheme is the perfective affirmative suffix *-dā/-a*, see §7.1.3.

4.4. Tonal phrases

There are several syntactic constructions in Mwan where tonal processes occur between their components (more precisely, the tone of the first component influences the tone of the second component). These constructions are the following:

- the genitival construction $N_{\text{dep.}} + N_{\text{head}}$;
- the attributive construction $N + \text{Adj}$;
- the syntactic group of a direct object and a transitive verb, $N_{\text{obj}} + V$;
- the syntactic group of a subject and an intransitive verb, $N_{\text{Sbj}} + V$;
- the postpositional phrase, $N + \text{Postp}$.

For the processes taking place within the tonal phrase, see §6.1.

5. Stress and tone; culminativity; prominence; obligatoriness

5.1. Culminativity

Mwan tone is not culminative: one word form can contain more than one toneme.

5.2. Stress

Mwan has no stress.

5.3. Positional prominence

Mwan has no positional prominence.

5.4. Obligatoriness of tone

Tone is not obligatory: there is a number of toneless words, see §4.3.

6. Tonal rules. Segmental rules which have incidence on tones

6.1. Tonal rules

Tonal rules are applied within tonal phrases (about tonal phrase, see §4.4). The order of application of the tonal rules is the following:

Stage 1:

H toneme copying with a L toneme deletion

H toneme copying on a toneless segment

L toneme copying

Stage 2:

L toneme dissimilation (OCP)

Stage 3:

Fusion of identical L tonemes on a heavy foot

H tone spread

Default M tone assignment to toneless syllables

6.1.1. H toneme copying with a L toneme deletion

If a word begins with a L toneme and the preceding word within a tonal phrase ends in a H toneme, the H toneme is copied on the subsequent syllable(s) thus erasing one L toneme (5).

(5) /dḏḏ/ [L dḏ][L ḏ] ‘husband’ → é dḏḏ [H é][H dḏ][L ḏ] ‘your (sg.) husband’

H toneme is not copied on the words of the “constant” type, i.e. those with initial M tone or those L-tone words which have a prefixed floating M diacritics, see §8.2.

The H toneme copy rule replaces a L toneme with a H toneme and does not impact the TDI.

6.1.2. H toneme copying on a toneless segment

If a word begins with a toneless syllable(s), and the preceding word within a tonal phrase ends in a H toneme, the H toneme is copied on the subsequent syllable(s) thus occupying the originally toneless space (6).

(6) /dã/ ‘wife’ → é dḏ ‘your (sg.) wife’

H tone is not copied on the words of the “constant” type, i.e. those with initial M tone, see §8.2.

This rule creates a new toneme and increases the Tonal Density Index.

6.1.3. L toneme copy

If a word begins with a toneless syllable(s), and the preceding word within a tonal phrase ends in a L toneme (here again, with the exception of the 3sg. subject pronoun *è[#]* and 3sg. non-subject pronoun *à[#]*), the L toneme is copied onto the toneless segment.

This rule is necessarily followed by the L tone dissimilation rule (see §6.1.5).

(7) /ti/ ‘uncle’ → (*Sità ti*) → *Sità tí* ‘Sita’s uncle’.

The L Toneme Copy Rule creates a new toneme.

6.1.4. L toneme dissimilation (OCP)

If a word begins with a L toneme, and the preceding word within a tonal phrase ends in a L toneme, the initial L toneme of the second word is replaced by H.

(8a) /yd̥ɛɛ/ ‘eye’ → d̥ɛ̃ yd̥ɛ̃ [L d̥ɛ̃][H yd̥ɛ̃] ‘child’s eye’

This rule is also applied in a sequence of L tonemes associated with different feet within a compound word. It is not applied to a sequence of two L tonemes within one heavy foot.

The 3SG pronouns /à[#]/, /è[#]/, /ò[#]/ do not licence the dissimilation of the subsequent L tone (8b).

(8b) à yd̥ɛ̃ /à[#] yd̥ɛ̃/ [L à][L yd̥ɛ̃] ‘his eye’

The L tone dissimilation rule does not concern words of the “constant” type, i.e. those with a prefixed floating M diacritics, see §8.2.

6.1.5. Fusion of identical L tonemes within a heavy foot

If each syllable of a heavy foot is assigned a L toneme at the underlying level and the initial L toneme is not replaced by H through the L toneme dissimilation rule, both L tonemes are fused into one, e.g. /kpàà/ → [L kpàà] ‘dry’ (rather than *[L kpà][L à]).

(About the difference between heavy feet of CV̇V̇ and CV̇V, see §8.2).

6.1.6. H tone spread

If an affirmative perfective form of a verb belonging to a mobile type (see §8.2) is preceded within a tonal phrase by a word that ends in a H toneme, this H toneme spreads on the initial syllable of the verb, thus resulting in the shrinking of the grammatical L-tonal span. See (9a) where a perfective form appears with its grammatical L tone after a M-tone word, and (9b) where the H tone of the direct object noun spreads on the verb.

(9a) Jàdà á bāā fāā-dā.
lion 1SG.POSS chicken steal-PRF
‘A lion has stolen my chicken’.

(9b) Jàdà á kpé fāā-dā.
lion 1SG.POSS duiker steal-PRF
‘A lion has stolen my duiker’.

In the case of a -dā-verb, the H toneme spreads on its initial foot (and the grammatical L tone appears on the suffix).

For more details on the tonal behavior of the affirmative perfective forms of verb, see §7.1.1.3.

H tone spread rule is also applied in postpositional groups with postposition dā ‘under’ where it results in a falling tonal contour on one syllable, see §3.1.2, example (2a).

The H tone spread rule has no incidence on the Tonal Density Index: it does not erase tonemes (instead, it modifies the boundaries of tonal spans) and does not create new tonemes.

6.1.7. Default M tone assignment to toneless syllables

If a toneless syllable acquires no tone through the H toneme copy rule or L toneme copy rule, it surfaces with a default M tone. This M tone is not considered a toneme.

6.2. Rules concerning segmental units which can affect the tonal density

There are no segmental rules affecting the tonal density.

7. Grammatical tones

7.1. List of grammatical tones

7.1.1. Habitual

The Habitual is expressed by a tonal morpheme MH. The M component is mapped on the verbal stem, e.g. kú ‘to catch’ → kū̄ ‘(he) catches’, bɔdā ‘to swell’ → bɔdā̄ ‘(it) swells’. The H component surfaces only on the dā-verbs and the verb d̄ɔciè ‘cook’, it is mapped onto the final foot (10).

(10) Bāā būdā á yd̄ tā.
hen bend REFL egg on
‘Hen broods eggs’ (< būdā ‘bend, brood’).

A verb in Habitual carrying a M tone is not impacted by the tones of the preceding word.

7.1.2. Imperative and Optative Affirmative

The Imperative-Optative affirmative tonal morpheme can be represented underlyingly as a floating M tone. It surfaces as a M tone on the final syllable of the verbal stem if this stem is represented by a heavy foot: *sóó* ‘to chew’ → *sóō* ‘chew!’, *bdáá* ‘to swell’ → *bdáā* ‘swell!’ If the lexical tone of a verb is M or its stem is represented by a light foot, the floating M morpheme is deleted.

7.1.3. Affirmative Perfective

7.1.3.1. Basic information on the affirmative Perfect morphology

The affirmative Perfective is formed jointly by (a) a tonal morpheme L mapped onto the verbal stem (this mapping takes place after the application of the tonal rules of the stages 1 and 2, see §6.1), and (b) a toneless suffix whose form depends on the weight of the preceding foot: after a light foot, *-a*, and after a heavy foot, *-da*. The suffix is assimilated by the nasality feature by the preceding foot, and it is integrated into its tonal span.

Light oral foot: *sí* ‘take’ → *sìà* [L *sìà*].

Light nasal foot: *gḥ* ‘sell’ → *gḥā* [L *gḥā*].

Heavy oral foot: *síí* ‘call’ → *sììdā* [L *sììdā*].

Heavy nasal foot: *gāā* ‘hide’ → *gāādā* [L *gāādā*].

The distribution of the allomorphes of the perfective suffix can be explained through phonotactical constraint: the short variant *-a* cannot be attached to a heavy foot, because this would lead to the creation of an extra-heavy foot (**sììà*, **gāāā*) disallowed in Mwan. For this reason, the full form *-da* has been retained only after a heavy foot. However, even this “strong” allophone of the perfective suffix displays characteristics which put under question its status of a full-fledged foot: it is nasalized by the preceding foot, and it is integrated into its tonal span (otherwise, if the suffix *-da* would host a separate L toneme, one would expect its replacement by H through the L toneme dissimilation rule).

7.1.3.2. Affirmative perfective of the *da*-verbs

The *-dā*-verbs represent a special case. In the affirmative perfective, the suffix *-a* is added to the derivative suffix *-dā* thus forming a heavy foot *-dāa*; the verbal stem acquires a L tone, and the final stem acquires a H tone, e.g. *dūdā* ‘to stop’ → *dūdāá*. This tonalization can be explained in the following way.

1) Grammatical L tone is mapped onto the verbal stem (i.e., the initial foot of the verb); the toneless suffix *-a* joins the derivative suffix *-dā* whose L toneme spreads on the perfective suffix.

2) According to the L toneme dissimilation rule (see §6.1.4), the final foot changes its L tone to H.

dūdā + ^L*-a* → (*dūdāà*) → *dūdāá* [L *dù*] [H *dāá*]

The tonal behavior of the verb *dḥciè* ‘cook’ follows the same logic as that of the *dā*-verbs. Its affirmative perfective form is *dḥciédā*. The following stages of its derivation can be postulated:

1) Grammatical L tone is mapped on the verbal stem *dḥ-* → *dḥ-*; the toneless perfective suffix joins the final component *-ciè* whose L toneme is copied on the perfective suffix. The choice of the allomorphe *-dā* of the perfective suffix is explained by the fact that the preceding foot is heavy. *-dā* does not constitute one tonal span with *ciè* (probably, it can be integrated into the tonal span of the verbal stem only, and not into the tonal span of the non-verbal component like *ciè*);

2) the L toneme of *ciè* is replaced by H through the L toneme dissimilation rule. Tone of *-dā* remains low.:

dḥciè → (*dḥciédā* [L *dḥ*][L *ciè*][L *dā*]) → *dḥciédā*.

7.1.3.3. H tone spread in the affirmative Perfective

If a perfective verbal form is preceded by a word ending with a H tone, this H tone is spread onto the verbal stem (see §6.1.5) if the verb does not belong to the constant type (see §8.2).⁵ However, this H tone spread does not result in erasing the perfective L tone replacive morpheme; the L toneme of this morpheme shrinks to the limits of the perfective suffix (11, 12).

(11) *á* *kú-á*.
1SG>3SG catch-PFV

⁵ In particular, application of this rule shows that all the verbs with the initial lexical H tone belong to the “mobile” type, i.e., they have no floating M to the left.

- ‘I caught it’ (< *kú* ‘catch’).
 (12) *á búé-dà.*
 1SG>3SG miss-PFV
 ‘I missed it’ (< *bùè* ‘miss’).

Cf. a verb of the constant type to which the H tone spread rule is not applied (13).

- (13) *á gǎǎ-dǎ.*
 1SG>3SG hide-PFV
 ‘I hid it’ (< *gǎǎ* ‘hide’).

In the *dà*-verbs of the mobile type, this rule results in a shift of the tonal melody rightwards (14).

- (14) *Í tásá é búdà-á gbɔ́ é díí.*
 1SG cup ART bend-PRF pot ART in
 ‘I covered the pot with the bowl’ (< *búdà-á* ‘bend-PFV’ < *būdà* ‘bend’).

In compound verbs of N+V type (see §2.2.3), the L toneme of Perfective is spread on the verbal stem. If the verbal stem belongs to the mobile type, a H-final tone of the nominal stem spreads onto the verbal stem:

kpéédédí ‘to forget’ (< *kpéé* ‘inner part’ + *dé* ‘lip’ + *dí* ‘to loose’) → *kpéé-dé-díà* ‘forget.PFV’;
bóówó ‘to gain’ → *bóó-wòà* ‘gain.PFV’.

7.2. Tonal paradigms

The tonal inflection of verbs is represented in Table 4.

	Stem	Habitual	Imperative & Affirmative Optative	Perfective H_	Perfective M_ & L_
High tone					
CV	<i>kú</i> ‘to catch’	<i>á kú</i> ‘I catch it’	<i>à kú</i> ‘catch it!’	<i>á kúà</i> ‘I caught it’	<i>yà kúà</i> ‘he caught it’
CVV̄, CLVV̄	<i>tdéé</i> ‘to breathe’	<i>í tdéé</i> ‘I breathe’	<i>tdéé</i> ‘breathe!’	<i>í tdéédà</i> ‘I breathed’	<i>è tdéédà</i> ‘he breathed’
-dà-verbs	<i>kpádà</i> ‘to stretch oneself’	<i>í kpádà</i> ‘I stretch myself’	<i>kpádà</i> ‘stretch yourself!’	<i>í kpádàà</i> ‘I stretched myself’	<i>è kpádàà</i> ‘he stretched himself’
Constant					
CV	<i>gǔ</i> ‘to sell’	<i>á gǔ</i> ‘I sell it’	<i>à gǔ</i> ‘sell it!’	<i>á gǔà</i> ‘I sold it’	<i>yà gǔà</i> ‘he sold it’
CV	<i>#gbí</i> ‘to chase’	<i>á gbí</i> ‘I chase it’	<i>à gbí</i> ‘chase it!’	<i>á gbíà</i> ‘I chased it’	<i>yà gbíà</i> ‘he chased it’
CVV̄, CLVV̄	<i>gǎǎ</i> ‘to hide’	<i>á gǎǎ</i> ‘I hide it’	<i>à gǎǎ</i> ‘hide it!’	<i>á gǎǎdà</i> ‘I hid it’	<i>yà gǎǎdà</i> ‘he hid it’
CVV̄, CLVV̄	<i>#bdǎǎ</i> ‘to swell’	<i>í bdǎǎ</i> ‘I swell’	<i>bdǎǎ</i> ‘swell!’	<i>í bdǎǎdà</i> ‘I swelled’	<i>è bdǎǎdà</i> ‘it swelled’
-dà-verbs	<i>dūdà</i> ‘to stop’	<i>í dūdà</i> ‘I stop’	<i>dūdà</i> ‘stop!’	<i>í dūdàà</i> ‘I stopped’	<i>è dūdàà</i> ‘he stopped’
Mobile					
CV	<i>ye</i> ‘to see’	<i>á yē</i> ‘I see it’	<i>à yē</i> ‘see it!’	<i>á yàà</i> ‘I saw it’	<i>yà yàà</i> ‘he saw it’
CV	<i>dɔ</i> ‘to buy’	<i>á dɔ</i> ‘I buy it’	<i>à dɔ</i> ‘buy it!’	<i>á dɔà</i> ‘I bought it’	<i>yà dɔà (dùà)</i> ‘he bought it’
CVV, CLVV	<i>bdee</i> ‘to eat’	<i>á bdēē</i> ‘I eat it’	<i>à bdēē</i> ‘eat it!’	<i>á bdeà (bdàà)</i> ‘I ate it’	<i>yà bdeà (bdàà)</i> ‘he ate it’
CVV̄, CLVV̄	<i>bùè</i> ‘to miss (an aim)’	<i>í būē</i> ‘I miss’	<i>būē</i> ‘miss!’	<i>á búédà</i> ‘I missed it’	<i>yà búédà</i> ‘he missed it’
-dà-verbs	<i>būdà</i> ‘to bend’	<i>būdà</i> ‘I bend’	<i>būdà</i> ‘bend down!’	<i>í búdàà</i> ‘I bent’	<i>è búdàà</i> ‘he bent’

Table 4. Tonal paradigms of verbs

8. Tonal classes of words

8.1. Differentiation of parts of speech by tone

Verbs differ from other classes of content words by the absence of CVV stems with heterogeneous lexical tones (see §4.2). Verbs are also characterized by rich tonal inflection, see §6.1 and §7.

8.2. Tonal classes of words

8.2.1. “Constant” and “mobile” tonal classes

With respect to their underlying tonemic associations, content words⁶ (nouns, adjectives and verbs) can be subdivided into five tonal types:

- M-toned words;
- L-toned words;
- L-toned words with prefixed floating M (designated by a high-indexed hash, e.g. #*gbì* ‘chase’);
- H-toned words;
- toneless words (which surface as M-toned in the citation form or at the beginning of a phrase).

These types form two tonal classes:

- 1) “mobile” (L-toned, H-toned and toneless words), and
- 2) “constant” (M-toned and L-toned with a prefixed floating M).

The “mobile” words are subject to the tonal rules mentioned in §6.1. The “constant” words are not susceptible to these rules and are not influenced by their left context; in other words, M toneme serves a screen for the rules.

In fact, for the H-toned nouns, division into constant and mobile types is irrelevant. For the verbs with initial lexical H, the diagnostic context is the perfective affirmative construction after a word ending in H tone. In this context, all lexically H-toned verbs behave as mobile words, see §7.1.3.3.

The majority of mobile nouns are relational (i.e., names of body parts, kinship terms, etc.), however, some free nouns are also found in this class. Therefore, membership in this class is lexically (rather than semantically) conditioned.

The majority of the *dā*-verbs are mobile (i.e., their initial foot is toneless), but there is at least one verb of this group belonging to the constant type: *dūlā* ‘stop’. The verb *dōcìè* ‘cook’ is constant (i.e., its initial foot is M-toned).

8.2.2. Two sorts of L-toned heavy feet

The majority of mobile words beginning with a heavy foot carrying L tones on both syllables (i.e., Cṽṽ-words) acquire H tone on both syllables if preceded by L or H: *kòḍò* ‘hand’ → *dē̃ kóḍò* ‘child’s hand’. Here are some words of this type:

bádē̃ ‘horn’, *dāà* ‘leaf’, *dē̃* ‘front’, *dū* ‘mouth’, *kòḍò* ‘hand’, *yádē̃* ‘eye’, *yā* ‘wood’.

However, in some other cases, H tone is assigned to the first syllable only, e.g.: *kpàà* ‘dry’ → *bádòḍò kpàà* ‘dry rice’. Here are some other words of this type:

dāā ‘female’, *dōḍò* ‘husband’, *sàà* ‘mat’, *sòḍò* ‘reason’, *tàà* ‘grandfather’.

The difference in tonal behavior of these subclasses can be explained through the toneme assignment at the underlying level: words like *kòḍò* ‘hand’ bear one toneme and can be represented at the underlying level as /kòḍò/, and words like *kpàà* ‘dry’ carry two tonemes, /kpàà/. This difference surfaces only if such a word is preceded by H or L and its initial L toneme is replaced by H according to the rules described in §6.1.1, 6.1.3; otherwise, two identical tonemes on one heavy foot undergo fusion (see §6.1.6) and surface as one tonal span.

8.2.3. Heavy feet with different tonalization of their syllables

There are mobile words beginning with a heavy foot carrying heterogeneous lexical tones, the initial one being L. In such words, when the tonal rules are applied, only the tone of the initial syllable is replaced by H:

dāāgdō̃ē̃ → *dāāgdō̃ē̃* ‘younger brother’, *ddūādē̃* → *ddūādē̃* ‘nephew’, *wādē̃* → *wādē̃* ‘raw’, *yòḍò* → *yòḍò* ‘bad’.

There are also a small number of heavy foot words where the initial syllable is toneless, and the second one carries a toneme. Here too, only the initial syllable acquires H through tonal rules:

dī → *dī* ‘life’.

⁶ The tonal modifications distinguishing the “mobile” and the “constant” types concern only the initial foot or even the initial syllable of a word. However, for the sake of simplicity, we speak of “constant and mobile words”, rather than feet or syllables: in fact, in the great majority of cases, a segment concerned by tonal modifications equals a word.

9. Diachrony of tones

Diachrony of tone in Mwan is unknown.

10. Tonal notation in the writing

Both writing systems created for Mwan are based on the Latin alphabet. Their use is very limited; there are only single speakers of Mwan who master it well, and some dozens who have followed literacy courses (either in the old or the new orthography) but have had very little practice ever since.

10.1. SIL Bolli and Flick's alphabet.

Surface tones of monosyllabic words are marked by symbols preceding the word: high tone by the apostrophe, low tone by the hyphen, mid tone by the absence of a sign, e.g. *'fē* /fē/ 'house'; *ye* /yē/ 'to see'; *-yi* /yì/ 'water'. Tonal marking on disyllabic words is ambiguous. If both vowels bear the same tone, only the tone of the first vowel is marked: *'peni* /pédí/ 'sting'; *bie* /bīē/ 'elephant'; *-vakɔ* /vákò/ 'sugar cane'. If the first vowel bears a low tone, and the second is "higher" (H or M), the word is followed by an apostrophe: *-gbaan* /gbàā'/ 'dog'; *-soo* /sòó/ 'horse'. If the tone of the first vowel is high, and the tone of second vowel is lower (L or M), the word is followed by a hyphen: *'pubɔ-* /púbɔ-/ 'to greet'; *'kpata-* /kpátà/ 'claire'. The mid tone on the first vowel is not marked, the high tone of the second vowel is denoted with an apostrophe, the low tone of the second vowel being denoted with a hyphen: *kɔnɛ* /kōdĕ'/ 'bug'; *nina-* /dīdā'/ 'to return'.

For trisyllabic and longer words, only the tone of the initial vowel is denoted: *-amasrɔyi* /àbās̀ròyí/ 'because'; *laanima* /dāādīfā'/ 'upwards'; *'ɲkena* /ɲkĕdā'/ 'good morning'.

This system is used in the translation of the Bible.

10.2. New orthography.

Since 2014, an alternative orthography for Mwan exists. In this orthography, surface tones are marked. L tone is designated by gravis, the H tone by acute, the M tone by the absence of diacritics: *bie* /bīē/ 'elephant', *gbàan* /gbàā'/ 'dog', *púbɔ* /púbɔ/ 'hello'.

11. Calculation of the Tonal Density Index

The text has been recorded from Azer Gogbé (born Kongasso 1990) in 2019 in Kongasso.

<i>Béè</i>	<i>dōodĕ</i>	<i>pĕgĕe</i>	<i>gdāawò</i>
[H 6é][L .è]	[M dō.ō][L - dĕ]	[M pĕ][H gé.é]	[M gdā.ā][L wò]
that	hare	and	hyena

The Tale of the Hare and the Hyena

<i>Béè</i>	<i>gbĕ</i>	<i>dàà</i>	<i>wà</i>	<i>é</i>	<i>tā</i>	<i>ézèzè.</i>
[H 6é][L .è]	[M gbĕ]	<[L dō.-à]>	[L wà]	[H é]	[M tā]	[H é-][L zè][L zè]
that	hunger	construct-PRF	village	ART	on	PREF-real

There was a real hunger in the village.

<i>Béè</i>	<i>dōodĕ,</i>
[H 6é][L .è]	[M dō.ō][L - dĕ]
then	hare-DIM

<i>è#</i>	<i>yàà</i>	<i>à#</i>	<i>bā</i>	<i>gbāda.</i>
[L è]	[L yà.à]	[L à]	[M bā]	[M gbā -dā]
3SG	COP.PRF	3SG.NSBJ	inside	in.field

He was in his field.

<i>Ké</i>	<i>ddī</i>	<i>tā</i>	<i>gbĭ</i>	<i>bū</i>	<i>é</i>	<i>ké</i>	<i>bū</i>
[H ké]	[M ddī.ī]	[M tā]	<[M gbĭ]>	[M bū]	[H é]	[H ké]	<[H bū]>
and	cow	on	chase.HAB	PL	ART	and	3PL.ANAPH

<i>gĕdĕ</i>	<i>wdaadĕ</i>	<i>yāa</i>	<i>gbā</i>	<i>é</i>	<i>yí.</i>
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[M gē][H -|dē] wdā.ā [M -|dē] [M yā.ā] [M gbā] [H é] [L yì]
 go-CONJ enter-SPN 3SG.POSS field ART in

And the shepherds came to the field.

Bō, è# yāa pē yāã gbā bū dá yà
 [M bō] [L è] [M yā.ā] [M pē] [M yā.ã] [M gbā] [M bū] <[H dá]> [L yà]
 well 3SG 3SG.POSS thing yam field PL REL 3SG>3SG

kpádē sàà,
 [H kpá][M -|dē] <[L sà.-à]>
 put-GER begin-PRF

béè ò bé yāã é kpé bdaà.
 [H bé][L .è] [L ò] [H bé] [M yā.ã] [H é] [H kpé] bdaà<[L -à]>
 then 3Pl 3SG.ANAPH yam ART all eat-PRF

He began to make a field of yams, and they ate everything.

Béè è# pe yē bé kédéé bé daa
 [H bé][L .è] [L è] pē [M yē] [H bé] [H ké][L |dē][H .é] [H bé] [H dá.á]
 then 3SG say hey! 3SG.ANAPH this.one 3SG.ANAPH NEG

sō kdēédè!
 <[M sō]> kdē.ē [H -|dē]
 can-HAB do-CONJ

And he says: Hey! this cannot be done!

Béè yéē dōodè è# ddi bū é bā-kpàà.
 [H bé][L .è] [H yé][M ē] [M dō.ō][L -|dē] [L è] [M ddi.ī] [M bū] [H é] [M mā]<[L |-kpà.-à]>
 then 3SG.EMPH hare 3SG cow PL ART go.after-PRF

And the hare followed the trail of the oxen.

Édūā dé tā zā bā sò gdōyā bū
 [H é-|dū][M .ā] [H dé] [M tā] [M zā] [M mā] [L sò] L [gdō.ò][M |-yā] [M bū]
 PREF-first INSTR surface reason on before hard-ABSTR PL

yàà sò bū kó.
 [L yà.à] [L sò] [M bū] [H kó.ó]
 COP.PRF before PL at

The affair of the past, the (mystical) power was with the ancestors.

Béè è# pe bdaa yéē yāã dá yò pòobī
 [H bé][L .è] [L è] pē [M bda.ā] [H yé][M ē] [M yā.ã] [H dá] [L yò] [L pò.ò][M -|bī]
 then 3SG say lie 3SG.EMPH yam REL COP such.person-AGNT

kpée bē,
 [H kpé.é] [M bē]
 belly here

fǒ pé yǎǎ é bǐ á bǎǎe dà
 [H fǒ] [H pé] [M yǎ.ǎ] [H é] [H bǐ] <[H á]> [H bǎǎ.é] [L dà]
 but first yam ART 1SG.EMPH 3SG.CTR.NSBJ eat FOC.NSBJ

wodè ézìη
 [H wó] [H -|dǎ] [H é-][L |zìη]
 do-CONJ again

He said: Lie! This yams which is in someone's belly, I must eat this yam too.

Bèè yéè pǐdǎǎ bǎǎyí,
 [H bǎǎ][L .è] [H yé][M .è] <[L pǐ]>[H |dǎ.-ǎ] [H bǎǎ][L .è][H |yí]
 then 3SG.EMPH jump-PRF so

béè è# wdāa dǎi é kpée.
 [H bǎǎ][L .è] [L è] <[L wǎ.-à]> [M dǎi.ǐ] [H é] [H kpé.é]
 then 3SG enter-PRF cow ART in

And he jumped up like this and entered into the belly of the ox (by magic).

Yǎǎ bǔ dá yò yē, ké yéè bǎǎ
 [M yǎ.ǎ] [M bǔ] [H dǎ] [L yò] [M yē] [H ké] [H yé][M .è] [H bǎǎ]
 yam PL REL COP there if 3SG.EMPH 3SG.ANAPH

sāsā é yē ké è# bǎǎ bǎǎē
 [M sā][M |sā] [H é] <[yē]> [H ké] [L è] [H bǎǎ] <[M bǎǎ.ē]>
 a.little ART see.HAB if 3SG 3SG.ANAPH eat.HAB

The yams that are over there, he sees a little bit and he eats.

àa! ké è pùèdā à bǎǎadē ò égbèdè
 [L à.à] [H ké] [L è] <[L pùè|-dǎ]> [L à] [M bǎǎ.ā][M -dē] [L ò] [H é-][L |gbè][L |dè]
 is.it if 3SG come.out-PRF 3SG.NSBJ get.fat-GER COP PREF-large

And when he came back, he gained a lot of weight.

béè gdāawò pē bǎǎyí káa dūdā
 [H bǎǎ][L .è] [M gdā.ā][L |wò] [M pē] [H bǎǎ][L .è][H |yí] [H ká.á] [M dū][L -|dǎ]
 then hyena say so that stop

And the hyena says so - see that! (surprised).

è! í yǎǎdè gù dǎè yí bē dǎǎ ké
 [L è] [H í] [H yǎ][L .à]<[L -|dǎ]> [L gù] [H dǎ][L .è] [L yí] [M bē] [H dǎ.ǎ] [H ké]
 oh! 1SG uncle-DIM famine this in here so.much if

bí ò pēbǎe yezí ké bí
 [H bí] [L ò] [M pē][M -|bǎǎ.e] [M yē][H -|zǐ] [H ké] [H bí]
 2SG.EMPH COP thing-eat see-PROG if 2SG.EMPH

bé bǎǎē èè?
 [H bǎǎ] <[M bǎǎ.ē]> [L è][L .è]
 3SG.ANAPH eat-HAB Q

Ah! my friend, in this famine, do you find food and do you eat?

káa bō yá pē bǎǎē é yá yézǐ
 [H ká.á] [M bō] [H yá] [M pē] <[M bǎǎ.ē]> [H é] [H yá] [H yé][M -|zǐ][H .í]

that well 2SG.POSS thing eat.HAB ART 2SG>3SG see-PROG

dǎǎ gbē zī ké yá bǎēē
[H dǎ.ǎ] [M gbē] [M zī] [H ké] [H yá] <[M bǎē.ē]>
so.much hand behind if 2SG.POSS eat.HAB

ké é bé gbēē bé à# pe á!
[H ké] [H é] [H bέ] [M gbēē][L .ē] [H bέ] [L à] pē [H á]
if 2SG 3SG.ANAPH manner 3SG.ANAPH 3SG.NSBJ say is.it

Well, your food, you find so much of it, tell me how you do it.

Abbreviations

- 1 — 1st person
- 2 — 2nd person
- 3 — 3rd person
- ABSTR — suffix of abstract nouns
- ADJ — adjective
- AGNT — agentive suffix
- ANAPH — anaphoric pronoun
- ART — article
- CONJ — conjunctive
- CONST — constant pattern
- COP — copula
- CTR — contrastive pronoun
- DAT — dative postposition
- DIM — diminutive suffix
- EMPH —emphatique pronoun
- FOC — focus marker
- GER — gerund
- HAB — habitual
- INSTR — instrumental postposition
- MOB — mobile pattern
- N — noun
- NEG — negation
- NSBJ — non-subject pronoun
- PL — plural
- POSS — possessive pronoun
- PREF — prefix
- PRF — perfective
- PROG — progressive
- Q — interrogative particle
- REFL — reflexive pronoun
- REL — relativisator
- SG — singular
- SPN — supin
- V — verb

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